

The alkali soil in Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh, had a loamy texture with initial pH 9.2, EC 1.4 dS/m, 38% exchangeable Na, hydraulic conductivity 0.019 cm/h, and 2.0% CaCO₃ for the surface 0-15 cm soil. Pyrites containing 22% S (4 t/ha) was applied at field moisture capacity. It was broadcast, mixed in the top 10-12 cm soil, and good quality tubewell water ponded for 1 wk to leach down soluble salts. Seedlings of 35-d-old Jaya rice were transplanted. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. Increasing pyrites fineness to 3 mm and allowing 1 wk before mixing pyrites into the soil increased yields significantly (see table). Applying 5-mm pyrites 1 wk before mixing into alkali soils was most efficient for reclamation. □

Effect of fineness and time of application of pyrites on rice yield and reclamation of alkali soil of Awagarh, Uttar Pradesh.

	Yield		Soil (0-15 cm) characteristics after rice				
	Grain (t/ha)	Straw (t/ha)	pH ₂	EC ₂ (dS/m)	ESP	HC (cm/h)	CaCO ₃ (%)
Pyrites fineness (mm)							
<3	3.58	6.40	8.40	.61	21	.067	0.68
3-5	3.34	5.28	8.57	.65	25	.064	1.01
5-10	2.71	5.00	8.86	.90	30	.034	1.50
Time (wk before mixing into soil)							
0	2.84	4.85	8.76	.83	29	.042	1.18
1	3.45	6.24	8.53	.71	24	.062	1.00
2	3.34	5.84	8.50	.64	23	.067	1.00
CD (0.05) for fineness or application time	0.42	0.88	0.09	0.10	3	.08	0.22

Response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields

B.H. Shahani, A.B. Khan, and M.B. Ahmad, Agricultural Research Station, D.I. Khan; and M. Ayaz Khan, Faculty of Agriculture, Gomal University, D.I. Khan, North-West Frontier Province, Pakistan

Rice response to three input factors — variety, plant population, and fertilizer — was studied in farmers' fields during 1985 kharif (wet season) at five locations using a randomized complete block design with three replications. The varieties tested were IR6 (local) and

Yield gap and percentage contribution of individual input factors. D.I. Khan, Pakistan, 1985 kharif.

Yield response of rice to input factors in farmers' fields. Pakistan 1985 kharif.^a

Level ^b of input factors			Yield (t/ha)
Variety	Plant population	Fertilizer	
F	F	F	3.4
R	F	F	4.4
F	R	F	4.3
R	R	F	5.4
F	F	R	4.4
R	F	R	4.6
F	R	R	5.0
R	R	R	6.5
LSD (.05)			1.4
(.01)			1.9

^aAV of 5 locations, 3 replications. ^bF = farmers' practice, R = recommended practice.

KS282 (improved). Plant populations were 125,000 and 250,000 hills/ha, and fertilizer rates were 75-22 and 120-40 kg NP/ha. All P and 50% N were applied before transplanting, and the remaining N was topdressed 30 d after transplanting. All other recommended cultural practices were followed.

The highest yield (6.5 t/ha) was produced by all recommended inputs,

followed by recommended variety and plant population (see table). The yield gap — 3.1 t/ha — was significant (see figure). Low plant population was the main constraint to high rice yield. □

N fertilizer (urea) topdressed on unsaturated soil and deep-placed using reflooding water

Chen Rongye, Zhang Jiancai, Guo Wangmo, and Chen Wei, China National Rice Research Institute (CNRRI), Hangzhou, Zhejiang, China

We evaluated a simple, practical, and efficient technique for deep placement of urea topdressed in irrigated ricefields. The technique combined N fertilizer application with soil moisture control.

Urea was topdressed on drained ricefields and the fields reflooded immediately. The fertilizer was deep-placed in the reduced zone by the infiltrating water.

The experiment was laid out in a clay loam soil, pH 6.2, 3.28% organic matter, 0.22% total N, 0.06% total P, and 2.01% total K. Fertilizer N efficiency was substantially increased compared with conventional broadcasting of N fertilizer on flooded ricefields (see table). □

Effects of deep placement of urea by reflooding water.^a CNRRI experimental farm, Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Application method	Urea N applied (kg N/ha)				Grain yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein (%)	N uptake (kg/ha)	Utilization (%) of applied urea N	N efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
	BT ^b	10 DT ^c	30 DT ^c	Total					
Control	0	0	0	0	6.6 c	6.74	93 c	0	71
Surface broadcast	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.2 b	7.66	129 b	32 d	55
Deepplaced by water	0	56.25	56.25	112.5	7.4 a	7.78	145 ab	46 b	51
Surface broadcast	67.5	33.75	33.75	135.0	7.4 a	7.62	148 ab	41 c	50
Deepplaced by water	28.3	56.25	28.20	112.5	7.4 a	7.74	149 a	50 a	50

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bBefore transplanting. ^cDays after transplanting.

Potassium nutrition of rice

M.S. Zia, M. Aslam, and M. T. Rashid, Pakistan Agricultural Research Council, National Agricultural Research Centre, Soil Science Section, P. O., N.I.H., Park Road, Islamabad, Pakistan

We studied K nutrition of rice in a pot experiment using poor-fertility loam soil: 0.56% organic matter, 0.045% N, 1.8% P, 61 ppm K, pH 8.3, and EC 0.6 mmho/cm. Treatments are in the table.

Twentyday-old Basmati 370 seedlings were used. Half were dipped in 0.7% K₂SO₄ solution and half in distilled water. Fertilizer was 100 kg N and 44 kg P/ha.

Dipping seedling roots in a 0.7% solution of K₂SO₄ for 72 h before

Effect of K application method on rice growth, yield, and K concentration.^a Islamabad, Pakistan.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant	Straw yield (g/pot)	Grain yield (g/pot)	K concentration (mg/g)	
					Straw	Grain
Control	121.3 b	6.4 c	46.1 c	20.2 c	10.90 a	6.76 b
166 kg K/ha	124.0 b	13.3 b	49.9 bc	21.5 c	11.81 a	13.88 a
0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	132.3 a	16.0 a	61.7 a	29.5 a	13.10 a	17.03 a
166 kg K/ha +0.7% K ₂ SO ₄	126.0 ab	12.7 b	55.4 b	25.6 b	13.90 a	13.39 a
LSD (0.05)	7	2.5	11.1	3.5	4.4	

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

transplanting resulted in significantly taller plants, more of productive tillers per plant, and higher straw and grain yield. K concentration in straw was not significantly affected by the treatments, but K application method affected K

concentration in rice grain. When 166 kg K/ha was applied with root dipping, plant height, productive tillers, and straw and grain yield were slightly lower. □

Breaking dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

A.S. Halepyati, M.N. Sheelavantar, and L. A. Dixit, Agronomy Department, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad 580005, Karnataka, India

In an attempt to multiply seeds of *S. rostrata*, we planted on 19 Jun 1986 and harvested mature pods on 3 Nov 1986. In Mar 1987, practically no germination of seeds occurred, indicating the existence of dormancy. Attempts were made to break dormancy. Fifty seeds per treatment were arranged on soaked germination paper and kept in a germinator (25 °C). Germination was recorded daily to 7 d after treatment.

Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid

Germination of seeds of *Sesbania rostrata* as affected by various treatments. Dharwad, India, 1986.

Treatment	Germination (%)
Control	0
Hot water (60 °C for 5 min)	4
Gibberellic acid (GA ₃ 0.1%)	8
Sand scarification	8
Overnight soaking in water	12
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 20 min	28
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 25 min	44
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 30 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 35 min	88
Soaking in concentrated sulfuric acid – 40 min	96

was most effective in breaking dormancy (see table). However, there was considerable variation in

germination with time of treatment. Germination increased from 28% with 20 min to 96% with 40 min. □

Influence of paclobutrazol on rice seedling growth

Pan Rui-chi, Biology Department, South China Normal University, Guangzhou, China

Rice Bai You Zhan No. 33 seedling growth was influenced by a soil drench of paclobutrazol granules at the one-leaf stage. Treated seedlings had faster leaf growth, shorter and stronger seedlings, higher tiller numbers, richer chlorophyll content, stronger rooting ability, and somewhat greater chilling resistance (see table). □